

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D6.4

CRM-GEOTHERMAL VIDEO CONTEST

Summary:

This report provides a description of the CRM-geothermal video contest organised within the *Task 6.3 Implement communication measures of WP6 Dissemination communication and exploitation*.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the CRM-geothermal Video Contest organised within the framework of the *WP6 Dissemination communication and exploitation, Task 6.3 Implement communication measures*.

The main goal of the video contest was to create awareness among European students about the role of geothermal energy in the energy transition, the importance of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) for our everyday life and the different faces of mining in Europe.

2 CONTEST ORGANISATION

2.1 CONTEST SCHEDULE

The contest was launched on 7 November 2023. The initial deadline for submitting video proposals was 14 April 2024. However, it was later extended to 24 June 2024 allowing more participants to send submissions.

2.2 ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The target participants were secondary school students: teenagers between 12-18-year-old across Europe. They were invited to participate and channel their creativity and passion into a video addressing the following subjects:

- The key role of geothermal in fighting climate change
- The importance of CRM in their everyday life and/or
- The importance of mining in their area

Participants could prepare a video individually or as a part of their class or a team.

The technical requirements for participating were the following:

- Language: The language of the video had to be English, but participants could use their native language with subtitles in English.
- Format: There were no restrictions on the video format, but HD, H264, and MP4 were recommended.
- Duration: The recommended duration for the video was no longer than 2 minutes. However, they could also send a longer video instead
- Size: The file size needed to be less than 1 GB.

When submitting a video participants had to fill in a form with the necessary information (name, surname, age, country), provide a consent form signed by their parents to comply with GDPR and upload their video.

The contest attracted an incredible array of talent and creativity, highlighting the importance of geothermal energy and Critical Raw Materials through engaging videos.

2.3 PROMOTION OF VIDEO CONTEST

The CRM-geothermal Video Contest was widely promoted by the European Federation of Geologists (EFG) with the key support of all [project partners and Affiliated Entities](#).

EFG designed promotional cards to promote the contest and set up a promotional website page including all the information about how to participate. This page is available at the following link on the CRM-geothermal website: <https://crm-geothermal.eu/2023/11/07/crm-geothermal-video-contest-for-12-18-years-old>

Figure 1: Promotional card for the CRM-geothermal Video Contest.

In addition, EFG produced [a short promotional video clip](#) to promote the contest on Instagram and TikTok. The promotion in these two social media channels was key to address teenagers directly, as they use these channels a lot, especially TikTok.

The 18 Affiliated Entities of the CRM-geothermal project, which are National Associations of EFG from different European countries promoted the contest at the national level. Their support was key, as some of them had direct and good contacts with schools and could communicate in the national languages. When possible, they directly contacted schools to share the CRM-geothermal Video Contest information. In addition, most of them promoted the contest with their networks through email, social media, and outreach events.

The Affiliated Entities contacted approximately 1080 schools across Europe.

2.4 COMPLEMENTARY RESOURCES

The promotional post comprised a section called 'Educational material for teachers' collecting relevant and related resources for teachers in different EU languages to encourage the discussion of CRM-geothermal related topics at school and provide contextual information for participants. As part of Task 6.5, D6.5, the collection of educational materials will be further expanded and distributed.

2.5 SUBMISSIONS

In total, 16 valid video submissions were received for the CRM-geothermal Video Contest. 26 students from 8 different countries in Europe participated as it can be seen in Table 1:

Table 1: Number of videos per country received for the CRM-geothermal Video Contest.

Country	Number of Videos
Portugal	4
UK	4
Bulgaria	2
Germany	2
Czech Republic	1
Italy	1
Serbia	1
Slovenia	1
Total	16

It was possible to participate individually or as a part of a team. 9 of the 16 submissions were individual participants, as ti can be consulted in Table 2:

Table 2: Participating individually or as a part of a team.

Country	Number of Videos
Individually	9
Teams	7
Total	16

The total number of participants in the contest were 26, counting all the individuals and team members. There were more girls participating than boys, as it can be seen in Table 3:

Table 3: Gender of participants.

Country	Number of Videos
Female	19
Male	7
Total	26

More than half of participants were 16-17 years-old, as it can be seen in the Table 4:

Table 4: Age of participants.

Age	Number of participants
12	6
13	1
14	2
15	3
16	7
17	7
Total	26

All of the video submissions can be found in the following playlists of the CRM-geothermal YouTube Channel:

- Finalist Videos (5 videos):
https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6YI2PYNfyXrXOpBBP9omXcR_M4Dz_QCE
- Participants Videos (11 videos):
https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6YI2PYNfyXqvEO4J7x3U_IJQgtKc_c3X

2.6 EVALUATION

There was a two-stage evaluation:

- Jury evaluation
- Public vote

In the first round, a jury narrowed down the number of entries to the best movies (up to 5 movies). The jury was composed of members of the EFG Panel of Experts on Education and members of the CRM-geothermal Stakeholder Board. The jury took into consideration the following aspects to evaluate the videos:

- Theme/Idea/Style
- Artistic value
- Technical implementation

The 5 finalist movies selected by the jury were uploaded to the CRM-geothermal TikTok, Instagram and YouTube channels.

Figure 2: Screenshot of finalist video uploaded to Instagram for the public vote.

Figure 3: Screenshot of finalist video uploaded to TikTok for the public vote.

These social media channels are the most used by teenagers (especially TikTok). The public audience could vote for their favourite videos by liking them on the social media channels previously mentioned from 11 July to 23 July 2024, 12:00 CEST.

Figure 4: Promotional card for the public vote of the CRM-geothermal Video Contest.

The three prizes were awarded based on the votes of the audience. The winners of the CRM-geothermal contest are the following:

- First Place: 'A Hope for Our Future' by Aurora Zaffino (Italy):
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UCHXws3-FU>
- Second Place: 'How geothermal solves the CRM climate crisis' by Tom Knight (UK):
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eJXTi5QMZxQ>
- Third Place: 'Geology with George' by Mari Symonds and Kayleigh Sandeman (UK):
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zhJxONKpclA>

2.7 PRIZES

The prizes for winners have been already purchased and delivered, they are the following:

- First place: Gift card (200 EUR) + Table of periodic elements (with element samples inside) + Puzzle of the Earth
- Second place: Gift card (150 EUR) + The Minerals Encyclopedia + Puzzle of the Earth
- Third place: Gift card (100 EUR) + Puzzle of the Earth

Figure 5: Card promoting the prizes for the CRM-geothermal Video Contest.

2.8 PROMOTION OF SUBMISSIONS AFTER CONTEST

The videos submitted that were neither finalists nor winners will be also promoted on a social media campaign in 2025.

3 IMPACT OF THE CONTEST

The promotional website page where all the information was available and where the videos could be submitted has received 2.690 visits making this page the second most visited of the CRM-geothermal website after the Home Page.

Figure 6: Number of visits to the CRM-geothermal Video Contest website page.

The shortened linked used to promote this page received approximately 1.100 clicks.

Figure 7: Number of clicks to shortened link for the CRM-geothermal Video Contest website page.

On the CRM-geothermal social media channels, the promotion campaign was intense. The table below shows the numbers of posts and the impressions/views received by these posts.

Table 5: Number of impressions/views of the Video Contest posts on social media (November 2023 – June 2024).

Social media channel	Number of posts/videos	Impressions, views
Instagram	15	1.757
TikTok	9	1.342
LinkedIn	12	6.450
X	13	5.630
Total	49	15.179

The posts on the Video Contest had a key role in increasing organic followers (+48) on Instagram between November 2023 and July 2024. In October 2023, before the contest's launch, the CRM-geothermal Instagram account had 107 followers. By the end of July

2024, after the winners were announced, the Instagram account had 155 followers. The contest's promotion supported a more rapid increase of followers on Instagram, compared to the previous trend. This is positive as Instagram is important to address a younger audience among the general public.

4 CONCLUSION

26 teenagers participated in the CRM-geothermal Video Contest, and 16 valid video submissions were received from 8 different European countries. The winners have been selected by a jury and a public vote on social media. The intense promotion on social media has contributed to the increase of followers in the project's accounts and the promotion of the project among younger Europeans.

The CRM-geothermal Video Contest has allowed teenagers, parents and teachers to learn more about the importance of geothermal energy, critical raw materials and mining in Europe. In addition, they could learn how the EU-funded project CRM-geothermal contributes to providing solutions to climate change and the supply of mineral raw materials in the European Union.